

METHODS OF GUIDING CAREER ORIENTATION IN THE INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT OF INDIVIDUALS AT EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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The strategic direction of the development of the education system in society is the intellectual and moral development of a person based on his purposeful independent activity in various fields. Along with the developed countries of the world, in our country, in the process of educational reforms, the promotion of independent education is an important direction. The research of the phenomenon of educating the professional competence of the pedagogue has been expressed in the works of a number of scientists. These authors put forward the opinion that together with the qualities of professional competence and reliability, they describe the pedagogical culture of the teacher as a professional-individual phenomenon. On the other hand, the concept of professional competence, as stated by V.A. Slastenin, represents the unity of the theoretical and practical readiness of the pedagogue to carry out pedagogical activities and describes his professional formation.

In the conditions of the market economy, the importance of choosing the right profession in people's well-being and activities, the requirements of various professions; world of professions, family tree of professions, important professions in the national economy of Uzbekistan, classifier of professions; training system of junior specialists; professions, working conditions, tools, science, purpose, students' interests and inclinations, the unique features of their character, their nervous structure, psyche, their abilities and needs to get information about the schools, the changing needs based on the requirements of the labor market of certain professions, the compatibility of the health with the chosen profession, in the secondary special, vocational educational institutions located in the region voluntary choice of education; opportunities to continue studying. He needs to know his future position.

Students can analyze professions; it is necessary to be able to correctly evaluate their personal qualities, interests and health levels, to be able to compare their individual characteristics with the demands of professions, and to make personal professional plans.

One of the important conditions for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the formation of a new system of training of highly trained personnel on the basis of the rich intellectual heritage of the people preserved for centuries and the new achievements of culture, enlightenment, science and technology and economy. Including, a number of changes are being introduced in the field of education and science. These changes will directly help the next generation to become a well-rounded person.

Formation of the literacy, knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for continuing general secondary education among students studying in educational institutions, providing students with the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications all the conditions have been created in order to develop their ability to think and analyze independently. Measures are

being taken on professional diagnosis and career guidance for the formation of primary knowledge and skills [1]. In this regard, the "Center for vocational guidance and psychological-pedagogical diagnosis of students" was established in our republic. This center helps students choose professions that match their interests, abilities and health, based on the needs of society and the requirements of the labor market, provided for by the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This center is responsible for the development and implementation of a unified state policy in the field of vocational guidance and psychological-pedagogical diagnosis of young students, organization of the republican system of vocational guidance of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, was established for the purpose of providing scientific-methodical, information-information and software.

Monitoring the state of vocational guidance and psychological-pedagogical diagnosis, taking measures to improve it, developing relevant programs, regulatory documents and recommendations; generalization, popularization and implementation of the best practices of our country and foreign countries; development of measures to improve the qualifications of specialists in psychological and pedagogical regional diagnostic centers and educational institutions charged with the task of guiding students of all levels to the profession; Working with priority programs and problems related to the realization of the life and professional identity of students of general secondary schools is one of the most important tasks of the republican diagnostic center [2, 21-b].

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education stipulates that students should study in vocational schools, colleges and technical institutes based on their chosen profession and specialization. In recent years, in our country, special attention has been paid to improving the fields of education and science, increasing respect for teachers and pedagogues, scientific and creative intellectuals in our society, and developing the professional skills of students. .

According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the development of education, training and science in the period of new development of Uzbekistan", starting from the 2021-2022 academic year, graduates of general education institutions will be able to show their talent and "Professional Orientation System" was introduced so that they can choose a profession that suits their interests, find a worthy place in society, and succeed in their professional activities. Choosing a profession is the most important step in a person's life.

There have been several attempts to systematize occupations based on required skills. Originally proposed by D Paterson in 1953. Let's focus on systematization of professions. It is very common and is based on 9 different skills. Using the Minnesota Occupational Rating Scale (MORS), 432 occupations are selected by professional psychologists and divided into the following 7 groups. Academic, mechanical, social, religious, musical, artistic and physical groups [3]. As a result of summarizing the results, 432 professions were brought into 214 samples, of which 137 are one profession and 77 combine two to 18 specialties.

Through interactive questionnaires and practical exercises, students will find answers to questions about the concept of profession and professions. They begin to have an idea about the professions they want to occupy in the future. Also, the meaning of the word "profession" means an occupation that serves as a source for people's craft, type of activity and living. And if this activity is a favorite, a person will definitely enjoy his life. Profession is a consciously chosen path of activity. The professions chosen by students should match their abilities,

interests, and character traits. Because the chosen profession should benefit not only them, but also the society. Ye.A. Klimov puts forward several definitions in this regard. The description is as follows: "A number of vocational orientation activities are selected for high school students based on their age characteristics.

Activities such as "Determining students' interests", "Professions and a person's suitability for a profession", "Understanding the professional identity of a school student", "Alphabet of career guidance" are conducted by school psychologists, interest abilities are determined, and they deal with each of the students individually and give the necessary recommendations. Seminar-training sessions will be conducted on the topic "My future profession". During the seminar, students will be guided to the professions they want to acquire in the future. Students' opinions on professions are listened to. Also, in determining the components of the intellectual components that ensure the formation of interest in the profession, the following are separate should pay attention to:

- Analysis and synthesis;
- Attention and observation;
- Separation and generalization;
- Classification and proof

At present, career guidance by Harrison Assessments method is the first and unique career guidance method in Uzbekistan, which will help you determine which specialty to choose for your child and which strengths to develop.

Through this test method we:

- We can analyze ourselves and our strengths;
- We can find out the list of professions that will be successful for us;
- We can analyze our leadership qualities;
- We can make a clear plan in our life in advance;
- We save our lives from wasted time and money;
- We have individual interviews and consultations with psychologists and specialists.

Vocational guidance is a system of activities aimed at helping professional self-determination. The purpose of career orientation is to determine the inclination of a person to a certain professional activity. This practice is based on the idea that every child is talented and can apply his talent in a certain field. There are various methods of career guidance — interviews with a teenager who is faced with choosing a future profession, with experts who discuss his interests and hobbies, as well as standardized methods, the results of which allow understanding of strengths and weaknesses.

References:

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